

Localization of Historical House Sites in Austria

Methodological Approach and Exemplary Case Studies

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Comments, suggestions, and additions are welcome.

This study addresses the localization of historical building sites based on individual historical references, such as address mentions in sources including newspapers or parish registers. The objective is the precise spatial assignment of these sites within the present-day landscape.

To this end, a methodological approach is presented that combines different types of sources and achieves reliable results through the correlation of multiple independent criteria.

The method is illustrated by means of a case study from Klagenfurt-Annabichl (Annabichl No. 4, vulgo Michitz).

1. Introduction

This study is part of an ongoing research project concerned with the identification and georeferencing of historical building sites (vulgo names and historical addresses) in Austria.

A systematic compilation of corresponding evidence is documented in the dataset “Vulgo Names and Historical House Identifiers in Carinthia” (Szekely 2026, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18959659).

While the dataset records a large number of localizations in condensed form, the present study aims to demonstrate the methodological derivation and verification process in detail through selected case studies.

2. Objective

The objective of this study is the precise spatial assignment of historically documented building or farmstead sites within the present-day landscape.

The starting point consists of individual historical references (e.g. addresses or vulgo names in newspapers, documents, or parish registers) that enable localization.

The focus lies on the methodologically transparent linkage of these references with the current cadastral structure.

3. Source Base

The localization is based on publicly accessible sources (online and on site) of different types and is adapted to the specific research question (selection):

- Address directories and address calendars
- Digital cadastral map (BEV)
- Servants' registers
- Franciscan Cadastre including parcel protocols
- Genealogical databases and digital source platforms
- Geographical information systems (e.g. KAGIS)
- Land registers
- Grey literature on specific regions, for example dissertations from local universities
- Historical maps and city plans
- Historical map portals
- Historical parish registers
- Historical newspapers and gazetteers
- Josephinian land survey
- Local historical literature
- Population registers

- Toponymic reference works (digital and printed)
- Municipal and city archives
- Theresian cadastre (Gültbuch)
- Urbars

4. Methodological Approach

The localization is carried out in several successive steps:

1. Identification of the building or farmstead site on the basis of historical references (address, vulgo name, personal associations) through systematic analysis of the available sources
2. Assignment to the building parcel in the Franciscan Cadastre, including comparison with parcel protocols where available
3. Transfer of the historical parcel into the present-day cadastral structure or assignment within the current cadastre (digital cadastral map, land register)
4. Georeferencing of the location within the present-day landscape using regional GIS data

An assignment is considered reliable only if multiple independent criteria coincide.

5. Limits of the Method

The present method is concerned with the localization of historical building or farmstead sites.

No direct identity between historical and present-day buildings can be inferred from this. In particular, continuity of address must not be equated with structural continuity.

A distinction must be made between three levels:

- **Building continuity:** the persistence of a specific physical structure over time
- **Structural continuity:** continuous construction at a given location, possibly involving successive replacement buildings
- **Address continuity:** the continuation of a designation or house number, potentially with slight spatial shifts

This differentiation is essential in order to avoid invalid identifications between historical and present-day buildings.

The temporal classification of sources is crucial for evaluating the assignment. References always relate to a specific point in time and must be interpreted within their respective historical context.

Spatial conditions are likewise subject to change. Relocation of building sites, re-parceling, and infrastructural transformations may lead to discrepancies between historical and present-day situations.

For periods prior to the Franciscan Cadastre (around 1828), precise spatial determination is generally only possible to a limited extent.

Changes in parcel structures and transformations through modern infrastructure must be taken into account.

6. Case Studies

6.1 Klagenfurt-Annabichl · Annabichl No. 4 · vulgo Michitz

The starting point of the investigation is the historical reference to the address “Annabichl No. 4” in the Klagenfurter Zeitung from the year 1844. Such references represent a typical starting point for local and settlement-historical research.

The subject of the investigation is the localization of the corresponding farmstead site within the present-day landscape.

Result

Location: Klagenfurt-Annabichl

Area: Henriquezweg / Alleegasse

Coordinates: 46.654548° N / 14.311542° E

Cadastral municipality: Ehrental

Status: no longer extant

The historical farmstead site could be clearly localized.

The sources used in this case are documented in the data sheet. The specific weighting and interrelation of the individual sources form part of the methodological procedure and are not disclosed here in detail.

7. Data Sheets

Data sheet 01 – Annabichl No. 4 · vulgo Michitz

The data sheet is available as a separate document.

8. Conclusion

The localization of historical building sites is, in many cases, clearly achievable on the basis of combined source material.

The applied method is transferable to comparable cases of historical address references.

9. Note

This document forms part of an ongoing research project on the identification and georeferencing of historical building sites in Austria. A summarized dataset is available under Szekely 2026 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18959659).

10. License

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11. Citation

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12. Archives and Databases

In the course of the research, the following archives and databases were consulted, among others:

Carinthian Regional Archives

Austrian National Library

ANNO – Austrian Newspapers Online

Matricula – Online portal for historical parish registers

Archive of the Diocese of Gurk

Arcanum Maps

Austrian State Archives

Library of the University of Klagenfurt

13. Versioning

Version 1.0 represents the first publication.

Future versions may include additional data sheets.

Appendix: Literature on the methodology of house name and settlement research (selection)

Ast, Hiltraud (2002):

Schwarzau im Gebirge: Der Markt, die Täler, die Höfe. Zeitreise durch eine historische Landschaft.

Schwarzau im Gebirge: Dorferneuerungsverein Schwarzau im Gebirge.

Čede, Peter (1991):

Die ländliche Siedlung in den Niederen Gurktaler Alpen: Kulturlandschaftswandel im Einzelsiedlungsgebiet unter dem Einfluss des Siedlungsrückganges.

Klagenfurt: Verlag des Geschichtsvereines für Kärnten.

Dehio-Handbuch (2001):

Die Kunstdenkmäler Österreichs. Kärnten.

Wien: Bundesdenkmalamt / Verlag Anton Schroll.

Hartwagner, Siegfried (1980):

Klagenfurt: Die Stadt und ihre Kunstwerke, historischen Lebens- und Siedlungsformen.

Salzburg: Verlag St. Peter.

Szekely, Brigitta (2026):

Vulgo Names and Historical House Identifiers in Carinthia (Austria). [Data set].

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